

Supplementary Figure 1. Original Questions for <i>in vivo</i> (18 questions) <i>in vivo</i> (21 questions)							
Test Substance Identification	Q1 (in vitro, in vivo) Was the test substance identified?	Q2 (in vitro, in vivo) Is the purity of the substance given?	Q3 (in vitro, in vivo) Is information on the source/origin of the substance given?	Q4 (in vitro, in vivo) Is all information on the nature and/or physico-chemical properties of the test items given, which you deem indispensable for judging the data (see explanation for examples)?			
Test System Characterization	Q5 (in vitro) Is the test system described?	Q6 (in vitro) Is information given on the source/origin of the test system?	Q7 (in vitro) Are necessary information on test system properties, and on conditions of cultivation and maintenance given?				
	Q5 (in vivo) Is the species given?	Q6 (in vivo) Is the sex of the test organism given?	Q7 (in vivo) Is information given on the strain of test animals plus, if considered necessary to judge the study, other specifications (see explanation for examples)?	Q8 (in vivo) Is age or body weight of the test organisms at the start of the study given	Q9 (in vivo) For repeated dose toxicity studies only (give point for other study types): Is information given on the housing or feeding conditions?		
Study Design Description	Q8 (in vitro) Is the method of administration given (see explanations for details)?	Q9 (in vitro) Are doses administered or concentrations in application media given?	Q10 (in vitro) Are frequency and duration of exposure as well as time-points of observations explained?	Q11 (in vitro) Were negative controls included (give also point, if not necessary, see explanations)?	Q12 (in vitro) Were positive controls included (give also point, if not necessary, see explanations)?	Q13 (in vitro) Is the number of replicates (or complete repetitions of experiment) given?	
	Q10 (in vivo) Is the administration route given?	Q11 (in vivo) Are doses administered or concentrations in application media given?	Q12 (in vivo) Are frequency and duration of exposure as well as time-points of observations explained?	Q13 (in vivo) Were negative (where required) and positive controls (where required) included (give point also, when absent but not required, see explanations for study types and their respective requirements on controls)?	Q14 (in vivo) Is the number of animals (in case of experimental human studies: number of test persons) per group given?	Q15 (in vivo) Are sufficient details of the administration scheme given to judge the study (see explanation for examples)?	Q16 (in vivo) For inhalation studies and repeated dose toxicity studies only (give point for other study types): Were achieved concentrations analytically verified or was stability of the test substance otherwise ensured or made plausible?
Study Results Documentation	Q14 (in vitro; Q17 in vivo) Are the study endpoint(s) and their method(s) of determination clearly described?		Q15 (in vitro; Q18 in vivo) Is the description of the study results for all		Q16 (in vitro; Q19 in vivo) Are the statistical methods for data analysis given and applied in a transparent manner (give also point, if not necessary/applicable, see explanations)?		
Plausibility of Study Design and Data	Q17 (in vitro; Q20 in vivo) Is the study design chosen appropriate for obtaining the substance-specific data aimed at (see explanations for details)?			Q18 in vitro (Q21 in vivo) Are the quantitative study results reliable (see explanations for arguments)?			
Supplementary Figure 1. Original Questions for <i>in vivo</i> (18 questions) <i>in vivo</i> (21 questions): Each row in Supplementary Table 1 represents one of the following group names: 1) Test Substance Identification, 2) Test System Characterization, 3) Study Design Description, 4) Study Results Documentation, and 5) Plausibility of Study Design and Data. If the question is related to <i>in vitro</i> and <i>in vivo</i> study design it is listed as Q1 (in vitro, in vivo). Then, if the question is listed differently for <i>in vitro</i> versus <i>in vivo</i> study design the questions are stacked above each other (e.g., Q5 (in vitro), Q5 (in vivo)).							